

The Butterfly Technique: A Novel Incision Design for Lip Repositioning

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Abstract

“Gummy smile” is a major concern for many patients visiting the dentist. Esthetics has now become an integral part of periodontal treatment planning. This article presents a case of a gummy smile in which esthetic correction was achieved through periodontal plastic surgical procedure wherein a 10–12 mm partial-thickness flap was dissected apical to the mucogingival junction, followed by approximation of the flaps. This novel technique gave excellent postoperative results with enormous patient satisfaction.

This surgical chairside procedure, being one of its kind with outstanding results, is very rarely performed by Periodontists. Thus, further clinical work and literature review are required. To make it a routine surgical procedure, this technique can be incorporated as a part of periodontal plastic surgery. Hence, we put forward a case with critical analysis of the surgical technique, including its limitations.

Keywords: Gummy smile, lip repositioning, periodontal plastic surgery

Introduction

A smile is an expression denoting pleasure, joy, happiness, or amusement. Smiling is something that is understood by everyone irrespective of one's culture, race, or religion. Smiling is a means of communicating emotions throughout the world.

A smile is an important gestural method of communication and is an interaction between the teeth, the lip framework, and the gingival scaffold¹. One of the most important or distinct features of dental and facial esthetics is the vertical anterior tooth display². Esthetic judgment is made by viewing the patient from the front in dynamic states like conversation, facial expressions, and smiling³.

The harmony of the smile is determined by the shape, the position, and the color of teeth and also by the gingival tissues. The gingival margin should be healthy and harmonious and today both patients and dentists are more aware of the impact of the gingiva on the beauty of the smile⁴ and particularly the periodontist can influence the appearance of the patient's smile.

The amount of visibility of the periodontium depends on the position of the smile line, which is defined as the relationship between the upper lip and the visibility of gingival tissues and teeth. The smile line is an imaginary line following the lower margin of the upper lip and usually has a convex appearance⁵. Few publications exist regarding the relationship between teeth and periodontium visibility during the smile⁶. Most dental professionals believe that during smiling the upper lip should position itself at the gingival margin of the maxillary central incisors⁷. However, it is known that displaying a certain amount of gingiva is esthetically acceptable and in many cases imparts a youthful appearance. Common cause of patient dissatisfaction is excessive gingival display. Patients may complain of a "gummy smile" and "short" maxillary anterior teeth⁸.

At least 50% of patients exhibit some form of gingival display in a normal smile⁹. However, exaggerated or forced smile patterns in up to 76% of all patients may exhibit gingiva. In absolute numbers, a normal gingival display between the inferior border of the upper lip and the gingival margin of the anterior central incisors during a "normal" smile is 1-2 mm¹⁰. In contrast, an excessive gingiva-to-lip distance of 4 mm or more is classified as "unattractive" by lay people and general dentists.

So it is very important to establish the etiology responsible for the excessive gingival display¹¹. Lip repositioning is suggested as an additional treatment modality for patients with lip hypermobility exposing undesired gingiva in a smile¹². This article gives a short review on lip repositioning and a case report of the surgical technique that was used to reduce gingival display¹³.

The objective of lip repositioning is to minimize the gingival display by limiting the retraction of the elevator smile muscles (e.g., zygomaticus minor, levator anguli oris, orbicularis oris and levator labii superioris) which is achieved by removing a strip of mucosa from the maxillary buccal vestibule and creating a partial-thickness flap between the mucogingival junction and the upper lip musculature¹⁴. The lip mucosa is then sutured to the mucogingival line, resulting in a narrower vestibule and restricted muscle pull, thereby reducing gingival display during smiling.

This technique was originally described as cosmetic surgery by Rubinstein and Kostianovsky¹⁵ for correction of a gummy smile caused by a hypermobile lip. This surgical procedure was designed to be shorter, less aggressive, and was thought to have fewer postoperative complications compared to orthognathic surgery. The procedure was advocated again by Litton and Fournier¹⁶ for the correction of excessive gingival display in the presence of a short upper lip. This was accomplished by detaching the muscles from the bony structures to coronally position the upper lip and no complications were reported. After a period of 25 years, two case reports again described this procedure¹⁷. The authors described good results. This technique is also termed as mucosal coronally positioned flap in a recently published case report¹⁸ wherein this technique demonstrates short-term successful use of this technique for the management of excessive gingival display in the presence of slight vertical maxillary excess and hypermobility of the upper lip. First case of lip repositioning done by an Indian dentist was by Gupta *et al*¹⁹.

Excessive gingival display is a major cause of patient embarrassment. An imbalance in the gingiva-tooth ratio results in gingival dominance, often referred to as a “gummy smile²⁰.”

A normal gingival display between the inferior border of the upper lip and the gingival margin of the central incisors during a normal smile is 1–2 mm. In contrast, a gingiva-to-lip distance of 4 mm or more is classified as unattractive²¹.

Etiologies of Excessive Gingival Display

- Delayed eruption: gingiva fails to migrate apically and reach 1 mm coronal to CEJ
- Vertical maxillary excess: enlarged vertical midface with incompetent lips
- Compensatory eruption: coronal migration of gingiva along with teeth
- Lip hypermobility: excessive upward movement of the upper lip during smiling

Surgical lip repositioning can reduce labial retraction of the elevator smile muscles, minimizing gingival display. First described in 1973 (Rubinstein & Kostianovsky), few dental reports exist, with cases by Rosenblatt & Simon (2006) and Gupta *et al.* (2010).

The objective of lip repositioning is to limit retraction of muscles like zygomaticus minor, levator anguli, orbicularis oris, and levator labii superioris, thereby reducing gingival display during smiling²².

Case Report

A 30-year-old woman reported with a chief complaint of a “gummy smile.” (fig1)

Fig- 1 gummy smile

- Examination: 3–4 mm excessive gingival display on smiling; normal tooth proportions; no medical contraindications.
- Treatment Plan: Lip repositioning surgery after informed consent.

Surgical Procedure

- Local anesthesia: Xylocaine 2% with epinephrine (1:100,000 and 1:50,000).
- Incisions:

fig 2 -Marking on mucosa

Fig 3- Horizontal incision

- First incision at mucogingival junction from right to left first molar. (Fig 3)
- Second incision 10–12 mm apical, parallel to the first.

Fig 4- Excision of tissue

Fig 5- butterfly shaped tissue exposed

- Elliptical outline created; epithelium removed leaving connective tissue exposed.

Fig 6- continuous interlocking suture

Suturing: Interrupted stabilization sutures (Maxon 6/0) at midline; continuous interlocking sutures for flap approximation. (fig 6)

- Post-op: NSAIDs (Ibuprofen 600 mg × 2 days), Amoxicillin 500 mg × 7 days, ice packs, restricted lip movement for 1 week.

Follow-up

- 2 weeks: Healing scar concealed in upper lip mucosa.
- 1 months: Stable reduction of gingival display; improved smile esthetics.

7 – Postoperative smile after 10 days

Preoperative smile

Postoperative smile

Discussion

Lip repositioning originated in plastic surgery and adapted to periodontics.

Variations include:

- With myectomies: detachment of smile muscles to prevent relapse.
- With spacers: preventing superior displacement of lip.
- Combined with rhinoplasty: for esthetic harmony.

Reported complications: minor swelling, bruising, mucoceles, rare paresthesia, or transient paralysis.

Contraindications

- Inadequate attached gingiva in anterior maxilla
- Severe vertical maxillary excess (requires orthognathic surgery)

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